

Addendum to “Thermal stability originates the vanishing of the specific heats at absolute zero”

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This Addendum acknowledges a previously overlooked 1971 work by I.P. Bazarov which anticipates the thermodynamic argument recently presented by the author [Phys. Scr. 100, 125206 (2025)]. I discuss the rarity of this reference and its absence from standard textbooks to ensure a complete historical record of the relationship between thermodynamic stability and the vanishing of specific heats.

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After publishing a thermodynamic proof of the Nernst theorem [1], my research focused on the vanishing of specific heat as temperature approaches absolute zero. While this phenomenon was historically addressed through the statistical models of Einstein [2], Debye [3], and Sommerfeld [4], I recently demonstrated that a purely thermodynamic explanation exists if one assumes that stability conditions hold in the vicinity of absolute zero [5].

Given the straightforward nature of this thermodynamic explanation, I suspected it might have been previously noted, though no such reference was identified during the original manuscript’s preparation. However, a recent review of historical literature I kept on my filing cabinet led to a work by Bazarov [6] regarding the Third Law of thermodynamics. While that work primarily critiques attempts to derive the Nernst theorem from the First and Second Laws, it contains the following significant remark:

“This corollary of the Third Law [the vanishing of the specific heats] can also be obtained from the Second Law. In fact, for non-equilibrium processes the Second Law leads to inequalities (sufficient conditions for the stability of the phase): $T/C_v > 0, T/C_p > 0$. For these inequalities to hold at $T \rightarrow 0$, it is necessary that $C_v \rightarrow 0$ and $C_p \rightarrow 0$ under these conditions.”

This source is an English translation of a Russian article originally published in *Zhurnal Fizicheskoi Khimii*.

To my knowledge, Volume 45 of this journal has not been digitized and lacks a DOI. At the beginning of the 21st century, I obtained a hard copy via an institutional library exchange, which has been scanned and uploaded to Zenodo doi:10.5281/zenodo.18880680 (currently embargoed due to copyright).

Notably, this discussion is absent from other major works by the same author, including his primary textbook [7] and his monograph on thermodynamic misconceptions [8].

The purpose of this Addendum is to formally acknowledge the early observation made by Bazarov [6] and to ensure the historical record of this thermodynamic argument is complete.

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[2] A. Einstein, Die plancksche theorie der strahlung und die theorie der spezifischen wärme, Annalen der Physik **327**, 180 (1907).
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- 83 [6] I. P. Bazarov, The third law of thermodynamics and its
84 derivations from the first and second laws, Russian Journal
85 of Physical Chemistry **45**, 927 (1971).
86 [7] I. P. Bazárov, *Thermodynamics*, edited by A. E. J. Hayes
87 (Pergamon Press, New York, 1964) (F. Immirzi trad).
88 [8] I. P. Bazárov, *Equivocaciones y errores en termodinámica*
89 (URSS, Moscú, 2003) (Jairo Correa Rodríguez/Aldo
90 Lorenzo Malca Paredes trad).

92 The significance of the work by Bazarov was
93 noted by J-MM-O when transferring his talk doi:
94 10.5281/zenodo.18434420 to a USB stick. The talk was
95 scheduled for the Conef-VII (Congreso Nacional de Es-
96 tudiantes de Física) held at Universidad de Extremadura
97 (RoR 0174shg90), Badajoz (Spain), 5–7 March 2026.
98 The USB stick contained the scanned version of Ref. [6],
99 which upon being accidentally re-read by J-MM-O al-
100 lowed the core issue to be identified at first glance.
101 Ref. [6] was promptly added to the talk, which inciden-
102 tally dealt with this problem.

103 The author expresses his sincere gratitude to the Board
104 of Conef VII for their kind invitation and warm hospi-
105 tality, and remains grateful to the attendees for the stim-
106 ulating environment.